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Comparative Assessment of Methods for Mathematical Modeling of Band Hydraulic Processes

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Abstract: *The article presents a comparative assessment of theoretical and experimental studies of channel hydraulic processes using the method of mathematical modeling.*

Key words: *river bed, modeling, analogy, Froude number, Reynolds number, method of mathematical (computer) modeling, two-dimensional computer model.*

Introduction. The parameters of hydropower and irrigation systems are determined by the capabilities of water users and natural historical factors (climate, topography, geology, terrain, etc.), and mainly depend on the volume of the flow of the rivers used. When creating, reconstructing and rehabilitating these systems, the main share of costs falls on hydraulic structures that ensure the supply of the required amount of water with a given quality, provided that the ecological safety of the watercourse is maintained and harmful effects of water flows are prevented.

The goal is a comprehensive hydraulic study of riverbed processes, to establish the relationship between riverbed parameters and hydraulic processes and hydromorphometric characteristics of rivers through mathematical (computer) modeling.

Main part. The method of mathematical (computer) modeling is widely used in calculations and forecasting of deformation processes of river channels and floodplains. At the initial stage of modeling, the main issue in the models is the development of a system of hydrodynamic equations of the studied channel process, convenient for determining the main physical and hydraulic processes in it. One of the main issues is achieving a more complete reflection of the channel process by the developed system of equations.

Sedimentation reduces the volume of water supplied to hydroelectric and irrigation systems and requires significant capital investment. This determines the need to study the characteristics of river

sediments and the transport capacity of flows in rivers where the sediment regime is complex due to the instability of channel processes, accompanied by periodic movements of large volumes of sediment deposits downriver in the form of ridges.

Sediments are solid particles of soil transported by moving volumes of water. In problems of sediment movement in liquid flows, the main characteristics are the particle diameter and their hydraulic size. The coefficient of hydrodynamic resistance is a function of the Reynolds number for the particles.

In the countries of the former Soviet Union, they use the hydraulic size scale of V.N. Goncharov, which is still being refined and improved:

1) for sediments with particle diameters less than 0.20 mm (laminar flow region at $Re d \leq 1$) $w = 0.66 d^2$, m/s (d , mm);

2) for sediments with particle sizes from 0.2 to 1.5 mm (transitional flow region at $1 < Re d \leq 300$) $w = 0.11 d^{1.04}$ m/s (d , mm);

3) for sediments larger than 1.5 mm (turbulent flow regime at $Re d > 300$) $w = 0.134 d^{0.5}$ m/s (d , mm).

Empirical relationships are recommended in the literature to determine some physical characteristics of sediment particles. As the results of numerous studies have shown, the rounded shape of large stones, gravel particles and pebbles is obtained as a result of water flowing around them when they stop or move more slowly [4]. After reaching a certain configuration, the rounding of the individual particles slows down or stops. At the same time, studies have shown that individual sediment particles are not subject to abrasion during their movement along the river, but are subject to the sorting process, which is actively manifested when passing channel-forming water flows.

Transport of sediments in a river bed depends mainly on their fractional composition, average water velocities, values of shear flow velocities relative to the parameters of sediment particles, depths, bottom slopes and free surface slopes. The flow's attraction capacity is estimated depending on the extent to which the average flow velocity exceeds the critical shear velocities of entrained sediments with an average diameter.

Traction sediments form a rough bottom of the river bed, to a greater or lesser extent forming numerous protrusions. The flow, touching these protrusions, forms eddies, tearing off individual particles from the upper layer, moves them, spending part of the energy on this, which reduces its speed. The transport of sediment particles depends on the nature of their resistance to the force action of water. The main criteria for the stability of particles in a natural river bed are: non-eroding water velocity; eroding water velocity.

Non-blurring v_d speed is any value of speed that is less than the erosive one. But, as a rule, it is understood as the limiting value of the average speed at which the development of erosion is excluded and at which sedimentation stops.

Boussinesq); from the former Soviet Union (N.E. Zhukovsky, N.S. Lelyavsky, A.M. Dementyev, V.N. Goncharov, N.F. Danelia, G.I. Zambakhidze, V.F. Talmaza) have devoted their work to the study of the movement of water flow containing sediments on curved sections of riverbeds. [1]

When moving on curved sections of river beds, a transverse circulation current caused by the redistribution of specific water consumption is added to the main longitudinal movement. The complexity of the phenomena that occur has not allowed us to solve the problem as a whole and develop a theoretically sound, practically tested method for calculating the movement of a two-phase

liquid flow (water - sediment) on river bends. This is also facilitated by the fact that today there is no unambiguous qualitative idea of the patterns of movement, and even more so, numerous local quantitative solutions are called into question.

In experimental studies of longitudinal and transverse circulation currents, on curved sections of river beds caused by the redistribution of specific water flow rates, the following similarities of laws were taken into account:

The ratio of gravitational forces is characterized by the similarity of the Froude number and the Reynolds number . The similarity of the numbers can be expressed as :

$$Fr_H \text{ ба } Fr_M = idem \quad Fr = \frac{v^2}{gh_{yp}} \quad (1) \text{ and } (2)$$

$$Re_M = Re_{np} = idem(3) \quad Re_M > Re_{np}(4)$$

Where Fr_n And Fr_m – the Froude number for a flow moving in nature and in a model, respectively; Re_{np} and Re_m are the Reynolds number for the flow moving in nature and in the model, respectively.

To simulate the study of unstable and stable water flow, a scale of 1:60 was adopted.

Based on the obtained similarity between the Froude numbers and the Reynolds numbers , we conclude that any change in the flow resistance forces leads to a change in the plane motion and a change in the limiting value of the Reynolds number .

In areas where local resistances appear, the limiting value of Reynolds numbers fluctuates within the range of 25,000÷120,000.

The use of mathematical apparatus makes it possible to calculate a specific hydraulic channel process of a real object and obtain results in a form convenient for the designer or operating service.

The system of equations used in computer models represents the flow motion in one, two and three dimensions respectively, with the main focus being on calculating the boundary conditions taking into account their change over time.

A one-dimensional computer model representing mainly the longitudinal movement of water flow can be represented as:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(QU + \frac{1}{2} \int_{Y_L}^{Y_R} h^2 dy \right) = gi\omega - \lambda \frac{Q^2}{\omega R} + F \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} \Big|_{z_b=const} + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial \omega S}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial QS}{\partial x} = -K(S - S_H) \quad (9)$$

$$\left(1 - p \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} \right) \Big|_{z=const} = -K(S - S_H) \quad (10)$$

where Q is the flow rate of two phases (water + solid particles - wastewater) moving in the channel ; t is time; $U = Q/\omega$ is the average flow velocity; ω is the cross-sectional area of the moving flow; g is the acceleration due to gravity; Y_L, Y_{np} are the coordinates of the left and right banks of the stream, respectively; $h = z - z_B$ is the depth of the flow; z is the water level mark (independent of the y coordinate); z_B is the channel bottom mark, $i = \sin\alpha$ is the inclination of the flow axis relative to the horizontal plane (α is the angle between them) ; λ is the coefficient of hydraulic resistance to friction - Darcy's coefficient; $R = \omega/\chi$ is the hydraulic radius; χ is the wetted perimeter; F is the specific force per unit length in relation to the density, taking into account the irregularity of the channel; S is the volumetric amount of suspended sediment particles in the flow; S_h is the transport capacity of the flow; K is the coefficient taking into account the degree of relationship between the flow rate and bottom sediments; ρ is the soil porosity. T is the ratio of voids in the soil to its natural volume.

In a one-dimensional mathematical model, equations (5) and (6) represent the law of conservation of momentum and mass of the flow. Equations (6) and (7) represent the deformation of the river. In these equations, is the flow at which real silting of the riverbed occurs.

The moving flow of water in the riverbed can be expressed in a two-dimensional computer model as:

$$\frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q_j U_j}{\partial x_j} + gh \frac{\partial z}{\partial x_i} = -\lambda Q_i \frac{|U|}{2h} - gh \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial x_i} \quad (i, j = 1,2) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$(1-p) \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial q_i^{(s)}}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$q_i^{(s)} = U_i + hs + D \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial x_i} \quad (8)$$

$$D = a_q h s |U| \left(1 - \frac{0,67 \alpha_w a_s |U|}{w(\alpha_b + \alpha_w |U|)/w} \right) \quad (9)$$

where: Q_i — components of specific discharge vectors; U_i — depth-averaged flow velocity; X_i — channel coordinates in plan; Z — water level marks of the flow; Z_d — river bed bottom marks; h — flow depth; λ — coefficient of hydraulic resistance to friction – Darcy coefficient; specific wastewater flow rate q_i^s ; ρ — porosity of the soil through which the channel passes ; D — coefficient characterizing the diffusion of the flow; α_g ; α_s ; α_b ; α_w — correction factors. For moving bottom sediments of liquids $\alpha_g = 3.3$; $\alpha_s = 0$; $\alpha_b = 0.24$; $\alpha_w = 0.01$; for suspended sediment particles in a flow $\alpha_g = 3.3$; $\alpha_s = 1.49$; $\alpha_b = 0.24$; $\alpha_w = 0.04$.

The computer model is based on the Saint-Venant system of equations [1].

These models were used in the study and calculation of deformation processes in sections of various lengths (3-5 km) of the Amu Darya and Sirdarya rivers , in places where water is collected without a dam with a flow turbidity fluctuating within the limits shown in Fig . 1 [2,3].

This model allows to calculate simultaneously the deformation of the banks and the bottom of the river bed (erosion and siltation), allows to take into account more fully the changes in the hydrodynamic parameters of the flow, it is possible to calculate the ebb and flow of currents. They calculate the two-layer water flow (the flow of water in the layer and above it). In this case, it is possible to obtain accurate results that take into account the morphometric changes of the bed.

One of the quantities used in solving the system of equations of numerical models is the turbidity of the flow, i.e. the transporting capacity of the flow. It is one of the components of the equation of liquid equilibrium. Empirical formulas used to calculate the transporting capacity of the flow have a special character for each condition. The use of theoretically based formulas gives a positive result, which is substantiated in laboratory studies and verified in natural observations. It should be added that these formulas require verification taking into account all local conditions.

In principle, if the initial condition is the shape of the river bed and the water level mark, then the boundary conditions are the calculated hydrograph at the entrance to the calculation zone and the soft conditions at the exit.

As a result of the analysis of the adopted mathematical apparatus of modeling, the relationship between nature and the model is determined. The following are taken as a basis: - a large-scale process in natural field conditions and the definition of the main criteria for modeling processes;

If it is possible to conduct research in several variants, a scientifically based rule for recalculating the parameters obtained in the model is formed.

With mathematical or computer modeling, it is possible to solve the mentioned system of hydrodynamic equations in different ways and obtain information about the dynamics of the parameters necessary for nature.

The disadvantage of computer models is the uncertainty of the degree of approximation. In practice, it is impossible to prove that a discrete problem corresponds to the initial solution. Compatibility must be justified. But despite the above-mentioned disadvantages, the scope of application of numerical studies to physical modeling is increasingly expanding.

Two-dimensional modeling can be performed at several scales smaller than the width of the channel and obtain the desired result for practice.

Conclusions.

Two- and three-dimensional modeling of channel process studies made it possible to conduct a series of experiments, on the basis of which the necessary parameters of sediment-saving and discharge devices were determined .

And the study of processes using numerical models, based on a system of hydrodynamic equations, is cost-effective. Calculations performed in several versions over a short period of time make it possible to clarify the essence of the process, the interaction of the flow and the channel itself.

One -dimensional mathematical models are the simplest in comparison with two- and three-dimensional mathematical models and allow for a fairly accurate study of fairly long sections of non-meandering river processes;

Two -dimensional mathematical models can be used at slightly larger scales in channel depth, but not larger than the mesoform size , with the limitation of river sinuosity;

Three- dimensional models are more complex models. Their use takes into account the curvature of the channel in three dimensions, longitudinal, transverse and circulation flow.

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